

Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Subtraction Algebra Rakhal Das^{1*} and Suman Das²

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Abstract: This paper aims to define the concepts of Semi-group and Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Subtraction Algebra. We also examine a few of their fundamental characteristics. Additionally, we provide a few appropriate instances on Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Subtraction Algebra.

Keywords: Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set; Subtraction Algebra, Subtraction Semi-Group.

1. Introduction:

Schein [30] developed the basic principles of Subtraction Algebra in 1992. Afterwards, Zelinka [37] presented the idea of subtraction semi-group. In the year 2004, Kyung et al. [26] presented some notes on subtraction semi-group. Later on, Jun and Kim [23] grounded the notions of ideal in subtraction algebra. In the year 2008, Jun and Kim [24] also studied the concept of prime and irreducible ideals in subtraction algebra. The concepts of Weak Subtraction Algebras were then grounded by Lee et al. [27], who also looked at a technique for creating Weak Subtraction Algebra from a quasi-ordered set. Zadeh [36] proposed the concept of fuzzy sets for the first time in 1963. Later, in 2007, Kim et al. [25] addressed the concept of fuzzy ideals in subtraction algebras. In 1986, Atanassov [3] constructed a new idea of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set by broadening the idea of Fuzzy Set. Ezhilarasi and Sriram [18] grounded the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy ideals of subtraction algebra. In 1998, Smarandache [31, 32] laid out the concept of Neutrosophic Set (NS) to aid in dealing with unpredictable occurrences with indeterminacy. In 2006, Vasantha Kandasamy and Smarandache [35] came up with neutrosophic algebraic structures in the context of neutrosophic set. In the year 2020, Ibrahim et al. [21] introduced the notions of Neutrosophic Subtraction Algebra and Neutrosophic Subtraction Semi-Group. Mallick and Pramanik [28] recently presented the principles of a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set by broadening the theories of NS, in which any component has a total of five independent components such as: truth, contradiction, ignorance, unknown, and false membership.

In this article, we introduce the notion of Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Subtraction Algebra and Semi-Group.

This article's remaining portion is structured as follows:

We review some pertinent definitions and findings on semi group and subtraction algebra in section-2. By extending the theory of neutrosophic subtraction algebra, we present the concepts of pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra in section-3. We also develop some findings regarding pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra. In section-4, we conclude this article.

2. Relevant Definitions and Results:

This section includes a few definitions and results that are fundamental to understanding the drafting of this article's primary outcomes.

Definition 2.1. [26] Let us consider a binary operation ‘-’ on a fixed set \tilde{A} . Then, the structure $(\tilde{A}, -)$ is referred to as a subtraction algebra if the following holds:

- (i) $\rho - (\rho - \rho) = \rho$;
- (ii) $\rho - (\rho - \rho) = \rho - (\rho - \rho)$;
- (iii) $(\rho - \rho) - \tilde{e} = (\rho - \tilde{e}) - \rho$; for all $\rho, \rho, \tilde{e} \in \tilde{A}$.

Remark 2.1. [26] Let us consider a subtraction algebra $(\tilde{A}, -)$. Then,

- (i) $\rho - 0 = \rho$ and $0 - \rho = 0$
- (ii) $\rho - (\rho - \rho) \leq \rho$.
- (iii) $\rho \leq \rho \Leftrightarrow \rho = \rho - w$ for some $w \in \tilde{A}$.
- (iv) $\rho \leq \rho \Rightarrow \rho - \tilde{e} \leq \rho - \tilde{e}$ and $\tilde{e} - \rho \leq \tilde{e} - \rho$ for all $\tilde{e} \in \tilde{A}$.
- (v) $\rho - (\rho - (\rho - \rho)) = \rho - \rho$.

Definition 2.2. [28] Let us consider that \tilde{A} be a fixed set. A pentapartitioned neutrosophic set (P-NS) \tilde{N} over \tilde{A} is defined by:

$$\tilde{N} = \{(\rho, T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho)): \rho \in \tilde{A}\},$$

where $T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \in]0,1[$ are the truth, contradiction, ignorance, unknown, falsity membership values of each $\rho \in \tilde{A}$. So $0 \leq T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) + C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) + G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) + U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) + F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \leq 5$.

The null P-NS (0_{PN}) and the absolute P-NS (1_{PN}) over \tilde{A} are defined as follows:

- (i) $0_{PN} = \{(\rho, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1): \rho \in \tilde{A}\}$;
- (ii) $1_{PN} = \{(\rho, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0): \rho \in \tilde{A}\}$.

Clearly, $0_{PN} \subseteq \tilde{N} \subseteq 1_{PN}$, where \tilde{N} is a P-NS over \tilde{A} .

Assume that $\tilde{N} = \{(\rho, T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho)): \rho \in W\}$ and $\tilde{H} = \{(\rho, T_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)): \rho \in W\}$ be two P-NSs over W . Then,

- (i) $\tilde{N} \subseteq \tilde{H} \Leftrightarrow T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \leq T_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \leq C_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \geq G_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \geq U_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho) \geq F_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)$, for all $\rho \in W$.
- (ii) $\tilde{N} \cap \tilde{H} = \{(\rho, \min\{T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), T_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \min\{C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \max\{G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \max\{U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \max\{F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}): \rho \in W\}$.
- (iii) $\tilde{N} \cup \tilde{H} = \{(\rho, \max\{T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), T_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \max\{C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \min\{G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), G_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \min\{U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}, \min\{F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), F_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)\}): \rho \in W\}$.
- (iv) $\tilde{N}^c = \{(\rho, F_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), 1 - G_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{N}}(\rho), T_{\tilde{N}}(\rho)): \rho \in W\}$ and $\tilde{H}^c = \{(\rho, F_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), U_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), 1 - G_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), C_{\tilde{H}}(\rho), T_{\tilde{H}}(\rho)): \rho \in W\}$.

Definition 2.3. [21] Assume that \tilde{A} be a fixed set. A set $\tilde{A}(I) = \langle \tilde{A} \cup I \rangle$ generated by \tilde{A} and I is referred to as an neutrosophic set. The members of $\tilde{A}(I)$ are of the form (ρ, yI) , where ρ and y are elements of \tilde{A} . I is referred to as an indeterminate and it has the property $I^n = I$ for all positive integer n .

Definition 2.4. [21] Let us consider a classical subtraction algebra $(\tilde{A}, -)$, and let $\tilde{A}(I) = \langle \tilde{A} \cup I \rangle$ be a set generated by \tilde{A} and I . Consider the neutrosophic algebraic structure $(\tilde{A}(I), -_N)$ where for all $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}I), (\tilde{w}, \rho I) \in (\tilde{A}(I), -_N)$ is defined by $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}I) -_N (\tilde{w}, \rho I) = (\hat{a} - \tilde{w}, (\tilde{e} - \rho)I) \forall \hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \tilde{w}, \rho \in \tilde{A}$.

We denote $(\tilde{A}(I), -_N)$ as a neutrosophic subtraction algebra.

An element $\rho \in \tilde{A}$ is represented by $(\rho, 0) \in \tilde{A}(I)$ and $(0, 0)$ represents the constant element in $\tilde{A}(I)$.

Definition 2.5. [21] Assume that $(\tilde{A}(I), -_N)$ be a neutrosophic subtraction algebra. Then, a non-empty subset $H(I)$ is referred to as a neutrosophic subtraction sub-algebra of $\tilde{A}(I)$ if the following conditions hold:

- (i) If $H(I) \neq \emptyset$
- (ii) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}I) -_N (\tilde{w}, \rho I) \in H(I)$ for all $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}I), (\tilde{w}, \rho I) \in H(I)$.
- (iii) $H(I)$ contains a proper subset which is a subtraction algebra.

If $H(I)$ does not contain a proper subset which is a subtraction algebra, then $H(I)$ is referred to as a pseudo neutrosophic subtraction sub-algebra of $\tilde{A}(I)$.

3. Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Subtraction Algebra:

In this section we established the concept of pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra on P-N-Ss, and established several results on it in the form of theorems, propositions, etc.

Definition 3.1. Assume that \tilde{A} be a fixed set. Then, a set $\tilde{A}(P_N) = \langle \tilde{A} \cup C \cup G \cup U \rangle$ which is generated by \tilde{A} and P_N is referred to as a pentapartitioned neutrosophic set. The members of $\tilde{A}(P_N)$ are of the form $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U)$, where $\hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \tilde{w}$, and μ are the elements of \tilde{A} . Here, C, G, U are called contradiction, ignorance, unknown and it has the property $C^n = C, G^n = G$ and $U^n = U$ for all positive integer n .

Definition 3.2. Assume that $(\tilde{A}, -)$ be any classical subtraction algebra. Suppose that $\tilde{A}(P_N) = \langle \tilde{A} \cup C \cup G \cup U \rangle$ be a set generated by \tilde{A} and P_N . Consider the pentapartitioned neutrosophic algebraic structure $(\tilde{A}(P_N), -_N)$ where for all $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \tilde{w}_1G, \mu_1U) \in (\tilde{A}(P_N), -_N)$ is defined as follows: $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U) -_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \tilde{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\tilde{w} - \tilde{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U), \forall \hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \tilde{w}, \mu, \hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \tilde{w}_1, \mu_1 \in \tilde{A}$. We call $(\tilde{A}(P_N), -_N)$ a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra.

An element $\alpha \in \tilde{A}$ is represented by $(\alpha, 0, 0, 0) \in \tilde{A}(P_N)$ and $(0, 0, 0, 0)$ represents the constant element in $\tilde{A}(P_N)$.

Theorem 3.1. Every pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra $(\tilde{A}(P_N), -_N)$ is a subtraction algebra.

Proof. Assume that $(\tilde{A}(P_N), -_N)$ is a subtraction algebra. Assume that $\alpha = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U), \gamma = (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \tilde{w}_1G, \mu_1U), z = (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \tilde{w}_2G, \mu_2U) \in \tilde{A}(P_N)$, where $\hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \tilde{w}, \mu, \hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \tilde{w}_1, \mu_1, \hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2, \tilde{w}_2, \mu_2 \in \tilde{A}$.

(i) We have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha -_N (\gamma -_N \alpha) \\ &= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U) -_N ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \tilde{w}_1G, \mu_1U) -_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U)) \\ &= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U) -_N ((\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e})C, (\tilde{w}_1 - \tilde{w})G, (\mu_1 - \mu)U) \\ &= (\hat{a} - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), (\tilde{e} - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}))C, (\tilde{w} - (\tilde{w}_1 - \tilde{w}))G, (\mu - (\mu_1 - \mu))U) \\ &= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \tilde{w}G, \mu U) \text{ Since } \hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \tilde{w}, \mu \in \tilde{A} \\ &= \alpha \end{aligned}$$

(ii) We have,

$$\alpha -_N (\alpha -_N \gamma)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \\
 &= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}((\hat{a}_1-\hat{a}), (\tilde{e}_1-\tilde{e})C, (\check{w}_1-\check{w})G, (\wp_1-\wp)U) \\
 &= ((\hat{a} - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1)), (\tilde{e} - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1))C, (\check{w} - (\check{w} - \check{w}_1))G, (\wp - (\wp - \wp_1))U) \\
 &= ((\hat{a}_1 - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a})), (\tilde{e}_1 - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}))C, (\check{w}_1 - (\check{w}_1 - \check{w}))G, (\wp_1 - (\wp_1 - \wp))U) \text{ Since } \hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \check{w}, \wp, \hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \check{w}_1, \wp_1 \in \tilde{A}. \\
 &= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)^{-N}((\hat{a}_1-\hat{a}), (\tilde{e}_1-\tilde{e})C, (\check{w}_1-\check{w})G, (\wp_1-\wp)U) \\
 &= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)^{-N}((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)) \\
 &= y^{-N}(y^{-N}\hat{\alpha})
 \end{aligned}$$

(iii) We have,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\hat{\alpha}^{-N}y)^{-N}z \\
 &= ((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U))^{-N}(\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U) \\
 &= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1), (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\check{w} - \check{w}_1)G, (\wp - \wp_1)U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U) \\
 &= (((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a}_2), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - \tilde{e}_2)C, ((\check{w} - \check{w}_1) - \check{w}_2)G, ((\wp - \wp_1) - \wp_2)U) \\
 &= (((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_2) - \hat{a}_1), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_2) - \tilde{e}_1)C, ((\check{w} - \check{w}_2) - \check{w}_1)G, ((\wp - \wp_2) - \wp_1)U) \text{ Since } \hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \check{w}, \wp, \hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \check{w}_1, \wp_1, \hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2, \check{w}_2, \wp_2 \in \tilde{A}. \\
 &= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_2), (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_2)C, (\check{w} - \check{w}_2)G, (\wp - \wp_2)U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \\
 &= ((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U))^{-N}(\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U) \\
 &= (\hat{\alpha}^{-N}z)^{-N}y
 \end{aligned}$$

From Vasantha and Smarandache [30] and Ibrahim et al. [18], we note that, if $\hat{\alpha} \leq y$ then we cannot in general say $\hat{\alpha}C \leq yC$, $\hat{\alpha}G \leq yG$, and $\hat{\alpha}U \leq yU$ it may so happen that $\hat{\alpha}C \leq yC$, $\hat{\alpha}G \leq yG$, and $\hat{\alpha}U \leq yU$. Thus, the pentapartitioned neutrosophic order in general needs not to preserve the order. If a set \tilde{A} is ordered under " \leq " then the pentapartitioned neutrosophic part of $\langle \tilde{A} \cup C \cup G \cup U \rangle$ may or may not have the preservations of order under \leq ; i.e., if $\hat{\alpha} \leq y$, $\hat{\alpha}, y \in \tilde{A}$ then $\hat{\alpha}C \leq yC$, $\hat{\alpha}G \leq yG$, and $\hat{\alpha}U \leq yU$ may occur or may not occur. For the work of the partial ordering we consider suppose $\hat{\alpha}C \leq yC$, $\hat{\alpha}G \leq yG$, and $\hat{\alpha}U \leq yU$ occur.

Theorem 3.2. For a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra $(\tilde{A}(P_N), ^{-N})$, the relation " \leq " is a partial order relation on $\tilde{A}(P_N)$.

Proof. Assume that $\hat{\alpha} = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)$, $\mu = (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$, $\theta = (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U) \in \tilde{A}(P_N)$ with $\hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \check{w}, \wp, \hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \check{w}_1, \wp_1, \hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2, \check{w}_2, \wp_2 \in \tilde{A}$.

(i) Since $\hat{\alpha} - \hat{\alpha} = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) = (\hat{a} - \hat{a}, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e})C, (\check{w} - \check{w})G, (\wp - \wp)U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ then $\hat{\alpha} \leq \hat{\alpha}$.

(ii) Suppose that $\hat{\alpha} \leq \mu$ and $\mu \leq \hat{\alpha}$.

Then, $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ implies $(\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\check{w} - \check{w}_1)G, (\wp - \wp_1)U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$

and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ implies $((\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e})C, (\check{w}_1 - \check{w})G, (\wp_1 - \wp)U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$.

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)^{-N}(0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \\
 &= (\hat{a} - 0, (\tilde{e} - 0)C, (\check{w} - 0)G, (\wp - 0)U) \\
 &= ((\hat{a} - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1)), (\tilde{e} - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1))C, (\check{w} - (\check{w} - \check{w}_1))G, (\wp - (\wp - \wp_1))U) \text{ Since, } \hat{a} - \hat{a}_1 = 0, \tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1 = 0, \check{w} - \check{w}_1 = 0 \text{ and } \wp - \wp_1 = 0. \\
 &= ((\hat{a}_1 - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a})), (\tilde{e}_1 - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}))C, (\check{w}_1 - (\check{w}_1 - \check{w}))G, (\wp_1 - (\wp_1 - \wp))U) \text{ Since } \tilde{A} \text{ is a subtraction algebra} \\
 &= ((\hat{a}_1 - 0), (\tilde{e}_1 - 0)C, (\check{w}_1 - 0)G, (\wp_1 - 0)U) \text{ Since, } \hat{a} - \hat{a}_1 = 0, \tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1 = 0, \check{w} - \check{w}_1 = 0 \text{ and } \wp - \wp_1 = 0. \\
 &= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)^{-N}(0, 0C, 0G, 0U)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U).$$

(iii) Let $\alpha \leq \mu$ and $\mu \leq \theta$. Therefore, $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \leq (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$ and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \leq (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U)$.

$$\text{Then, } (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \text{ implies } (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\wp - \wp_1)U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$$

$$\text{and } (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \text{ implies } (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}_2, (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}_2)C, (\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w}_2)G, (\wp_1 - \wp_2)U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U).$$

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U) \\ &= (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_2, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_2)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_2)G, (\wp - \wp_2)U) \\ &= (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_2, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_2)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_2)G, (\wp - \wp_2)U) \\ &= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_2) - 0, ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_2) - 0)C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_2) - 0)G, ((\wp - \wp_2) - 0)U) \\ &= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_2) - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_2) - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1))C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_2) - (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1))G, ((\wp - \wp_2) - (\wp - \wp_1))U) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_1 - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1)) - \hat{a}_2, (((\tilde{e}_1 - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)) - \tilde{e}_2))C, (((\ddot{w}_1 - (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)) - \ddot{w}_2))G, (((\wp_1 - (\wp - \wp_1)) - \wp_2))U) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_1 - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a})) - \hat{a}_2, (((\tilde{e}_1 - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e})) - \tilde{e}_2))C, (((\ddot{w}_1 - (\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w})) - \ddot{w}_2))G, (((\wp_1 - (\wp_1 - \wp)) - \wp_2))U) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}_2) - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), ((\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}_2) - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}))C, ((\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w}_2) - (\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w}))G, ((\wp_1 - \wp_2) - (\wp_1 - \wp))U) \\ &= (0 - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), (0 - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}))C, (0 - (\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w}))G, (0 - (\wp_1 - \wp))U) \\ &= (0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \leq (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U)$. Consequently, “ \leq ” is a partial order relation.

Proposition 3.1. Assume that $(\tilde{A}(P_N), \text{--}_N)$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra . If $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \in \tilde{A}(P_N)$, with $\hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \ddot{w}, \wp \in \tilde{A}$, then the following are true:

- (i) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (0, 0C, 0G, 0U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U)$;
- (ii) $(0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$;
- (iii) $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$;
- (iv) $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$;
- (v) $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U)) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$;
- (vi) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U))) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$;
- (vii) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \leq (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$;
- (viii) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) = (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \Leftrightarrow (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U)$.

Proof. (i) We have, $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$
 $= (\hat{a} - 0, (\tilde{e} - 0)C, (\ddot{w} - 0)G, (\wp - 0)U) = (\hat{a} - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}), (\tilde{e} - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}))C, (\ddot{w} - (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}))G, (\wp - (\wp - \wp))U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U).$

(ii) $(0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) = (0 - \hat{a}, (0 - \tilde{e})C, (0 - \ddot{w})G, (0 - \wp)U) = (0 - (\hat{a} - 0), (0 - (\tilde{e} - 0))C, (0 - (\ddot{w} - 0))G, (0 - (\wp - 0))U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U).$

(iii) We have, $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U)$
 $= (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\wp - \wp_1)U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U)$
 $= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a}, ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - \tilde{e})C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - \ddot{w})G, ((\wp - \wp_1) - \wp)U)$
 $= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}) - \hat{a}_1, ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}) - \tilde{e}_1)C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}) - \ddot{w}_1)G, ((\wp - \wp) - \wp_1)U)$

$$= (0-\hat{a}_1, (0-\tilde{e}_1)C, (0-\ddot{w}_1)G, (0-\mu_1)U)$$

$$= (0, 0C, 0G, 0U).$$

(iv) $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U))^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$

$$= (((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a}_1), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - \tilde{e}_1)C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - \ddot{w}_1)G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - \mu_1)U)$$

$$= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - (\hat{a}_1 - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1)), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - (\tilde{e}_1 - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)))C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - (\ddot{w}_1 - (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)))G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - (\mu_1 - (\mu - \mu_1)))U)$$

$$= (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U)$$

$$= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$$

(v) $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U))^{-N}((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)) = (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U)^{-N}((\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e})C, (\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w})G, (\mu_1 - \mu)U) = ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - (\hat{a}_1 - \hat{a}), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - (\tilde{e}_1 - \tilde{e}))C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - (\ddot{w}_1 - \ddot{w}))G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - (\mu_1 - \mu))U) = ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a}_1, ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - \tilde{e}_1)C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - \ddot{w}_1)G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - \mu_1)U) = (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$

(vi) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U))) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a} - \ddot{w}, (\tilde{e} - \mu)I)) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U).$

$$= (\hat{a} - (\hat{a} - (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1)), (\tilde{e} - (\tilde{e} - (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)))C, (\ddot{w} - (\ddot{w} - (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)))G, (\mu - (\mu - (\mu - \mu_1)))U)$$

$$= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a}), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - \tilde{e}))C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - \ddot{w}))G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - ((\mu - \mu_1) - \mu))U)$$

Since from the properties of \tilde{A} , if $\hat{a}, \hat{a}_1 \in \tilde{A}$ then $(\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a} = 0$ then we have

$$((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - \hat{a}), ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - \tilde{e}))C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - \ddot{w}))G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - ((\mu - \mu_1) - \mu))U)$$

$$= ((\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1) - 0, ((\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1) - 0)C, ((\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1) - 0)G, ((\mu - \mu_1) - 0)U)$$

$$= (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\ddot{w} - \ddot{w}_1)G, (\mu - \mu_1)U)$$

$$= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$$

(vi) $((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)))^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = ((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U))^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \Rightarrow (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)) \leq (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$

(vii) Suppose that $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$. Then $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$.

$$= (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U))$$

$$= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U))$$

$$= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(0, 0C, 0G, 0U).$$

$$= (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$$

$$\Rightarrow (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U).$$

Conversely, suppose that $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)$
 Then, $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U) \Rightarrow (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U)^{-N}(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$ and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \mu_1U)^{-N}(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \mu U) = (0, 0C, 0G, 0U)$.

Definition 3.3. Assume that $\tilde{A}_1(P_N)$ and $\tilde{A}_2(P_N)$ be two pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra. Then, the direct product of $\tilde{A}_1(P_N)$ and $\tilde{A}_2(P_N)$ is denoted by $\tilde{A}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{A}_2(P_N)$ and defined as follows:

$$\tilde{A}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{A}_2(P_N) = \{((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) : (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \ddot{w}G, \wp U) \in \tilde{A}_1(P_N), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \in \tilde{A}_2(P_N)\}.$$

Proposition 3.2. Assume that $(\tilde{A}_1(P_N), -_N)$ and $(\tilde{A}_2(P_N), -_N)$ be two pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra. Then, $(\tilde{A}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{A}_2(P_N), -_N)$ is also a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra.

Proof. Suppose that $\alpha = ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U))$, $\mu = ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U))$, $\theta = ((\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \ddot{w}_4G, \wp_4U), (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \ddot{w}_5G, \wp_5U)) \in \tilde{A}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{A}_2(P_N)$, for all $\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0, \ddot{w}_0, \wp_0, \hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2, \ddot{w}_2, \wp_2, \hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4, \ddot{w}_4, \wp_4 \in \tilde{A}_1$ and $\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \ddot{w}_1, \wp_1, \hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3, \ddot{w}_3, \wp_3, \hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5, \ddot{w}_5, \wp_5 \in \tilde{A}_2$. Therefore,

(i) We have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha -_N (\mu -_N \alpha) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) -_N [((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) -_N ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U))] \\ &= ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) -_N [(\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U) -_N (\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U) -_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)] \\ &= (\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U) -_N ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U) -_N (\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U)), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) -_N ((\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U) -_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \\ &= \alpha. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) We have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha -_N (\alpha -_N \mu) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) -_N [((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) -_N ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U))] \\ &= ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) -_N [((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U) -_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U)), ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) -_N (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U))] \\ &= (\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U) -_N ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U) -_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U)), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) -_N ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) -_N (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) \\ &= (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U) -_N ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U) -_N (\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U)), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U) -_N ((\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U) -_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \\ &= ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) -_N [((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) -_N ((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U))] \\ &= \mu -_N (\mu -_N \alpha). \end{aligned}$$

(iii) We have,

$$\begin{aligned} & (\alpha -_N \mu) -_N \theta \\ &= [((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) -_N ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U))] -_N ((\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \ddot{w}_4G, \wp_4U), (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \ddot{w}_5G, \wp_5U)) \\ &= [((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U) -_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U)), ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) -_N (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U))] -_N ((\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \ddot{w}_4G, \wp_4U), (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \ddot{w}_5G, \wp_5U)) \\ &= (((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \ddot{w}_0G, \wp_0U) -_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \ddot{w}_2G, \wp_2U)) -_N (\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \ddot{w}_4G, \wp_4U)), ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \ddot{w}_1G, \wp_1U) -_N (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \ddot{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) -_N (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \ddot{w}_5G, \wp_5U) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \check{w}_0G, \wp_0U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \check{w}_4G, \wp_4U)) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U), ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \check{w}_5G, \wp_5U)) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \check{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) \\
 &= [((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \check{w}_0G, \wp_0U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \check{w}_4G, \wp_4U)), ((\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \check{w}_5G, \wp_5U))] \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \check{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) \\
 &= [((\hat{a}_0, \tilde{e}_0C, \check{w}_0G, \wp_0U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}_4, \tilde{e}_4C, \check{w}_4G, \wp_4U), (\hat{a}_5, \tilde{e}_5C, \check{w}_5G, \wp_5U))] \text{--}_N ((\hat{a}_2, \tilde{e}_2C, \check{w}_2G, \wp_2U), (\hat{a}_3, \tilde{e}_3C, \check{w}_3G, \wp_3U)) \\
 &= (\hat{\alpha} \text{--}_N \theta) \text{--}_N \mu.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3.3. Assume that $\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N)$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra. Suppose that A be a classical subtraction algebra. Then, the structure $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N) \times A, \text{--}_N)$ is a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra.

Definition 3.4. Assume that $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N), \text{--}_N)$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra. Then, if the following criteria are met, a non-empty subset $A(P_N)$ is referred to as a neutrosophic subtraction sub-algebra of $\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N)$:

- (i) $A(P_N) \neq \emptyset$;
- (ii) $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \in A(P_N)$, for all $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \in A(P_N)$;
- (iii) $A(P_N)$ contains a proper subset which is a subtraction algebra.

$A(P_N)$ is referred to as a pseudo pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction sub-algebra of $\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N)$ if it does not contain a proper subset that is a subtraction algebra.

Definition 3.5. Suppose that $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}, -, *)$ be any subtraction semi-group, and assume that $\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N) = \langle \tilde{\tilde{A}} \cup C \cup G \cup U \rangle$ be a set generated by $\tilde{\tilde{A}}$ and P_N . Then, $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N), \text{--}_N, *)$ is referred to as a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group. Let $(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U)$ and $(\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)$ be any two elements of $\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N)$ with $\hat{a}, \tilde{e}, \check{w}, \wp, \hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1, \check{w}_1, \wp_1 \in \tilde{\tilde{A}}$. Then we define the following:

$$(\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) \text{--}_N (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (\hat{a} - \hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e} - \tilde{e}_1)C, (\check{w} - \check{w}_1)G, (\wp - \wp_1)U),$$

$$\text{and } (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) * (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) = (\hat{a}\hat{a}_1, (\tilde{e}\hat{a}_1 + \hat{a}\tilde{e}_1 + \tilde{e}\tilde{e}_1)C, (\check{w}\hat{a}_1 + \hat{a}\check{w}_1 + \check{w}\check{w}_1)G, (\wp\hat{a}_1 + \hat{a}\wp_1 + \wp\wp_1)U).$$

Definition 3.6. The direct product of two pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-groups $\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N)$ and $\tilde{\tilde{A}}_2(P_N)$ is denoted by $\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{\tilde{A}}_2(P_N)$ and defined as follows:

$$\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{\tilde{A}}_2(P_N) = \{((\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U)) : (\hat{a}, \tilde{e}C, \check{w}G, \wp U) \in \tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N), (\hat{a}_1, \tilde{e}_1C, \check{w}_1G, \wp_1U) \in \tilde{\tilde{A}}_2(P_N)\}.$$

Proposition 3.5. Assume that $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N), \text{--}_N, *)$ and $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}_2(P_N), \text{--}_N, *)$ be two pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group. Then, $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}_1(P_N) \times \tilde{\tilde{A}}_2(P_N), \text{--}_N, *)$ is also a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group.

Proposition 3.6. Assume that $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N), \text{--}_N, *)$ be a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group, and suppose that $(A, -, *)$ be a classical subtraction semi-group. Then, $(\tilde{\tilde{A}}(P_N) \times A, \text{--}_N, *)$ is a pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group.

4. Conclusions:

The basic ideas of pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group and pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra have been examined in this paper. Further, the basic properties of subtraction algebra and subtraction semi-group have been analyzed and established. We believe that numerous fresh investigations can be executed in the years to come by

utilizing the concepts of pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction semi-group and pentapartitioned neutrosophic subtraction algebra.

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